
A Warming World, a Shrinking Space for Human Rights

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Abstract

Climate change is no longer an environmental issue. It has now become something much bigger, affecting people's basic rights such as the right to life, food, health, water, housing and livelihood. This Article looks at climate change from a human right perspective by examining international treaties, constitutional values and the way climate jurisprudence is evolving both in India and globally. We have laid emphasis on the Indian Constitutional Framework and judicial responses, highlighting how judiciary has gradually turned environmental concerns into enforceable legal rights.

Keywords: Climate Change, Environment, Deforestation, Pollution, Global Warming

Introduction

“Climate change means a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods.”³

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³ *United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (adopted 9 May 1992, entered into force 21 March 1994) 1771 UNTS 107 art 1.*

Climate change basically means the long term shift in temperature and weather patterns in a place. Is it mostly linked to human activities like burning fossil fuels, cutting down forests and industrial pollution, which increases greenhouse gases in the air. Because of this, the planet is getting warmer, Sea levels are rising and heat waves are becoming more common. At the same time, events like droughts, floods and cyclones are happening more often than before. These directly affect people's daily lives, their health and livelihood.

The United Nations Human Rights Council acknowledged in 2008 that climate change poses “an immediate and far-reaching threat to people and communities around the world.”⁴. This article explores that shift and examines how international law, constitutional principles and courts have responded.

Research Methodology

This article is based on a qualitative research approach based entirely on secondary sources such as international treaties, constitutional provisions, judicial decisions, UN resolutions and reports by organizations like the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change and World Health Organization. It examines how climate change impacts fundamental human rights particularly the rights to life, health, food, water, and shelter, especially for vulnerable communities. The study also compares India's climate governance with rights-based judicial approaches, using real life examples from cities like Delhi, Chennai, and Bengaluru.

Relationship between Human Rights and Climate Change

“Climate change is probably the greatest human rights challenge of 21st century.”

~Mary Robinson

⁴UN Human Rights Council, ‘Human Rights and Climate Change’ Res. 7/23 (28 March 2008).

(President, Mary Robinson Foundation-climate Justice)

Human rights and environmental protection are closely linked. Environmental degradation directly affects the basic conditions needed for people to actually enjoy their rights. The principle of inter-generational equity, as discussed in the Brundtland Report, lays reminds us that “present generations hold the Earth in trust for future generations.”⁵ in that sense , climate change challenges the legal thinking beyond immediate concerns , forcing us to consider the rights of future generation as well

Beyond the Brundtland report, the principle of inter generational equity is reflected in various international legal declarations such as:

- The 1972 Stockholm Declaration on the Human Environment recognizes the responsibility to protect and improve the environment for future generations.
- UNESCO Declaration (1997): The Declaration on the Responsibilities of the Present Generations towards Future Generations states that each generation inheriting the Earth “temporarily” should take care to use natural resources reasonably to ensure life is not prejudiced for future generations.
- Professor Edith Brown Weiss developed this principle in her 1989 book ‘Justice to Future Generations’, arguing that all generations hold the Earth “in common as a trust,” making us both beneficiaries and trustees.
- The Vienna Declaration reaffirmed that all human rights are universal, indivisible and interdependent.⁶

⁵World Commission on Environment and Development, *Our Common Future* (Oxford University Press 1987).

⁶Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action (25 June 1993).

Below we have discussed how rights such as right to life, food, health and water are affected due to climate change.

A. Climate Change and the Right to Life

Climate change poses a direct threat to the right to life⁷ protected in Article 6 of International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and recognised as a fundamental rights under Article 21 of Indian constitution. Increasing heat waves, cyclones, floods and irregular rainfall have already led to loss of life. This places a duty on the states to take both preventive and adaptive measures. If such steps are not taken, it raises serious concerns about the failure to protect the right to life itself.

B. Climate Change and the Right to Health

The right to health , recognized under Article 12 of the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) is also deeply affected. Climate change affects public health by increasing heat-related sickness, worsening air quality and disturbing access to clean water. Rising temperatures increases vector-borne diseases, while air pollution continue to increase respiratory conditions. The World Health Organisation estimates that climate change will cause approximately 250,000 additional death per year between 2030 and 2050.

C. Climate Change and the Right to Adequate Food

By disturbing agricultural cycles, climate change results in reduced crop yields and disrupted rainfall cycle, thereby imposing serious challenge to the right to adequate food which is essential for living a healthy life as is recognised in Article 21 of Indian Constitution. Food insecurity caused by climate change may, in turn,

⁷*International Covenant On Civil And Political Rights (adopted 16 December 1966, entered into force 23 March 1976).*

lead to malnutrition, hunger and several diseases. According to World Food Program, the number of people who are food insecure worldwide has increased from 135 million people (before the COVID-19 pandemic) to 280-300 million people in 2023. In 2022, 9.2% of the global population was undernourished.

D. Climate Change and the Right to Water

In some regions, rising heat, melting glaciers, unpredictable rain and droughts have led to water scarcity while in others, floods often contaminate water sources. The problem is not just scarcity but also unequal access. Some communities are it much harder than others.. From a human rights point of view, this means that states have to take responsibility for managing water in a fair and sustainable way.

E. Vulnerable and Marginalised Groups

According to the reports of Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), climate impacts are unevenly distributed. Those who have contributed the least to climate change often suffers the most. Indigenous people, elderly, migrants, coastal communities and economically weaker sections are more threatened to climate changes risks. The UN Human Rights Council in several resolutions has acknowledged that climate change is now an immediate and serious threat to people and communities, especially those already in vulnerable situations.

In *Daniel Billy and Others v. Australia* (Torres Strait Islanders petition), the UN Human Rights committee held that failure on part of Australia to mitigate the effect of climate change violate the right of indigenous island communities, specially the right to culture, under the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.

F. Women and children

Women and children are disproportionately affected by climate harms due to deep rooted social inequalities and physiological and economic vulnerability. Children are physiologically more prone to heat stress, and vector borne diseases. The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women requires State to address climate impact on women. The Convention on the Rights of Child protects children's right to survival and development.

Climate Governance versus Rights-Based Judicial Reasoning in India

A. Climate Governance in India

The primary climate framework in India is the National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC). Adopted by the Government of India in 2008, it integrates climate priorities with national development goals, protecting and restoring ecological balance.

The Plan has eight missions:-

- ✓ National Solar Mission (NSM),
- ✓ National Mission for Enhanced Energy Efficiency (NMEEE),
- ✓ National Mission on Sustainable Habitat (NMSH),
- ✓ National Water Mission (NWM),
- ✓ National Mission for Sustaining The Himalayan Ecosystem (NMSHE),
- ✓ Green India Mission (GIM),
- ✓ National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA), and
- ✓ National Mission on Strategic Knowledge for Climate Change (NMSKCC).

The NAPCC's structure reinforces nexus of climate change and human rights.

State-level policies include:-

- ✓ State Action Plans on Climate Change (SAPCCs).

Alongside this, cities have their own climate action strategies such as Mumbai Climate Action Plan, to deal with local challenges.

While these policies are necessary for climate action, they mostly treat climate change. As a technical or policy issue and rarely as something that directly affects basic human rights.

B. Rights-based Judicial Reasoning

Although the Constitution of India does not expressly recognize a right against climate harm, the Indian judiciary has played an important role in filling the void through liberal interpretation. It has consistently considered climate concerns as human rights issue.

Article 21⁸ guarantees the right to life and personal liberty to every person has been interpreted broadly by the Supreme Court to include the right to live in a clean, pollution-free, healthy and wholesome environment. Problems like Extreme heat, pollution, water scarcity and environmental deterioration, directly takes away, from the individual these rights.

Further, the Directive Principles of State Policy⁹ reinforce this constitutional vision. Article 48A requires the State to protect and improve the environment while Article 51A (g) places a similar duty upon citizens to care for natural resources.

⁸ *Constitution of India, 1950.*

⁹ *Constitution Of India, 1950.*

The Preamble of the Constitution of India speaks of “justice – social, economic and political.” But in reality, climate change does not affect everyone equally. Those who contribute the least like slum dwellers or marginalized communities often face the worst impacts, while more privileged groups are able to protect themselves to some extent, oxygen mask and air purifiers. Because of this, climate issues has also start becoming questions of fairness and justice.

In ***Subhash Kumar v. State of Bihar***¹⁰, the Supreme Court emphasised that the right to life includes right to pollution-free air and water.

Further, this idea was Strengthened in later cases. In ***M.C. Mehta v. Union of India***¹¹, the coach dealt with industrial pollution , affecting the ganga river, and held that such actions violate the right to life. Similarly, in ***Indian Council for Enviro-Legal Action v. Union of India***¹², the Supreme Court held that the environmental deterioration is directly affecting health and dignity.

In ***Vellore Citizens Welfare v. Union of India***¹³, the court recognised that groundwater pollution caused by tanneries imposed severe damage to health and livelihoods. The court applied the polluter-pays principle. In ***T.N. Godavarman Thirumulpad v. Union of India***¹⁴, the Supreme Court highlighted the need to protect forests and wildlife not only for ecology but as also for human survival and interpreted Article 48A¹⁵ and Article 51A (g)¹⁶ in that light.

Integration: Bridging Policy and Judicial Reasoning:- The relationship between India’s climate governance framework and judicial intervention is both

¹⁰ *Subhash Kumar v. State of Bihar AIR 1991 SC 420.*

¹¹ *M.C. Mehta v. Union of India 1988.*

¹² *Indian Council for Enviro-Legal Action v. Union of India AIR 1996 3 SCC 212.*

¹³ *Vellore Citizens Welfare v. Union of India AIR 1996 SC 2715.*

¹⁴ *T.N. Godavarman Thirumulpad v. Union of India AIR 1997 2 SCC 267.*

¹⁵ *Constitution of India 1950.*

¹⁶ *Constitution of India 1950.*

complementary and policies fall short in implementation while judicial decisions are case-specific. But together, they show the climate change is also a human rights issue.

Actions Taken By International Human Rights Mechanism

Since 2008, the Human Rights Council have been actively looking at how climate change affects human rights, The Council held two round table conferences on human rights and climate change, which was also the theme of the 2010 Social Forum¹⁷. Following resolutions on human rights and climate change have been adapted to date:

- **Resolution 7/23**¹⁸ : Emphasis on “climate change poses an immediate and far-reaching threat to people and communities around the world” and also asked the OHCHR to study the relationship between climate change and human rights.
- **Resolution 10/4**¹⁹ : Expressed that “climate change-related impacts have a range of implications, both direct and indirect, for effective enjoyment of human rights...” and that such effects “will be felt most acutely by those segments of the population who are already in a vulnerable situation...”
- **Resolution 18/22**²⁰ : the Council asserted that “human rights obligations, standards, and principles have the potential to inform and strengthen international and national policy-making in the area of climate change, promoting policy coherence, legitimacy, and sustainable outcomes.”

¹⁷ UNHRC Report of the Social Forum A/HRC/16/62.

¹⁸ March 2008.

¹⁹ March 2009.

²⁰ September 2011.

- **Resolution 26/27²¹**: stretch the need for cooperation between states , including sharing resources, technology, and knowledge to deal with climate challenges , particularly in developing countries.

Overall, the council has made it clear that climate change is not just an environmental issue, but a global human right concerns, and that addressing it requires collective efforts and coordination at the international level.

COP21²² Recommendations

The 21st Conference of the Parties (COP) to United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change was held at Paris, France, during the span of 30th November to 11th December, 2015. The Conference adopted the historic Paris Agreement, a call for global action against the global issue of climate change. It aimed at ensuring to keep the earth's temperature between 1.5°C to 2°C. It is regarded to be a landmark moment whereby the developed as well as developing nations came together to fight the leviathan of climate change. The nations agreed on following recommendations:-

- Appointment of a Special Rapporteur on human rights and climate change to identify good practices, strengthen accountability mechanisms, engage with the Secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and further explore the links between climate change and human rights;
- Thorough integration of human rights obligations, standards and principles in international and national climate policy and action, including COP 21;

²¹ July 2014.

²² 21st Conference Of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention On Climate Change (Paris, 30 November-21 December 2015).

- Participation of all relevant stakeholders in the development and implementation of climate change policies and action;
- Mitigation and adaptation efforts that place people at the centre, are gender sensitive, and ensure the rights of persons, groups and people in vulnerable situations, including women, children, indigenous people and the poor. These could be informed by the use of impact assessments to ensure that climate actions benefit those facing the greatest risks;
- Improved regulation of the private sector in order to mitigate their contributions to climate change and ensure their respect for human rights in all their actions;
- Enhanced cooperation based on principles of equity and fairness to ensure adequate funding and research into adaptation measures to help the poorest countries and those persons, groups and peoples most at risk;
- Intensified research and development into renewable sources of energy and energy conservation to reduce the emissions intensity;
- Equitable access to technology, including, if necessary, the lowering of intellectual property standards and facilitation of technology transfer;
- The creation of a climate justice fund;
- Protecting and utilizing traditional knowledge of local communities and indigenous peoples to support the effective use of resources for agriculture and forestry;
- Titling the lands and territories of indigenous peoples and other communities in order to support preservation of forests and improved carbon storage;

- Utilizing community-based climate monitoring to reduce monitoring costs and enhance early warning systems;
- Improved capacity-building, development assistance, innovative finance and clean development mechanisms;
- Improved communication between climate change negotiators and human rights experts including through increased participation in the Geneva Pledge²³;
- Consideration by States of the linkages between human rights and climate change during the universal periodic review;
- Increased scrutiny of the impacts of climate change on human rights by Human Rights Council Special Procedure Mandate Holders;
- A special session of the Human Rights Council (HRC) on human rights and climate change; and
- The creation of a legal instrument to protect the rights of climate affected people.

The above mentioned recommendations focus on a shared and collective responsibility of quality integration between the climate change and human rights keeping in mind the notion of mutual respect, protection and promotion of one another. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change provides for different scenarios for different action plans. Article 6 of the Paris Agreement provides for establishment and implementation of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs).

²³Launched in November 2024 by International Gender Champions, to ensure the fulfilment of goals agreed at the Paris Agreement.

Conclusion

Climate change is no longer just an environmental problem. It is slowly eating into basic human rights. what we are seeing now is not limited to damaging environment, the impact is visible across rights, like life, health, housing, food and livelihood. The increasing impact of climate change requires the urgent and immediate action not merely as environmental policy but as an instrument for the protection of human rights.

As observed by Mary Robinson, President, Mary Robinson Foundation - Climate Justice *“Time is running out to avoid dangerous climate change. This year, 2015, presents a unique opportunity to set the global community on a new path; away from fossil fuel based development and towards a sustainable alternative that will ensure the protection of the rights of generations to come.”*

This comprehensive understanding requires states to address inequalities and injustices that make certain groups more vulnerable, especially women, children and indigenous communities, by prioritizing the most affected a rights based approach lines effectively with the constitutional objective of justice and equity.

When the climate is injured, the rights get fractured;

A collective call is required to recover the rupture,

So come one, come all; let's fight the leviathan with collective efforts of us all.